

Boiled Potato Food Target Product Profile Workplan, at CIP-Peru & Uganda

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This report has been written in the framework of the RTBfoodomics project (under CIRAD coordination), as a continuation of work initiated under the RTBfoods and RTB Breeding projects.

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Ethics: The activities, which led to the production of this document, were assessed and approved by the CIRAD Ethics Committee (H2020 ethics self-assessment procedure). When relevant, samples were prepared according to good hygiene and manufacturing practices. When external participants were involved in an activity, they were priorly informed about the objective of the activity and explained that their participation was entirely voluntary, that they could stop the interview at any point and that their responses would be anonymous and securely stored by the research team for research purposes.

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ABSTRACT

The RTBfoodomics project officially started with a kickoff and planning meeting organized at CIAT (Cali, Colombia) in March 2025. This gathering brought together the partners of the project to align on project activities and responsibilities. Defining a standard sampling protocol was of particular importance.

Following the meeting, CIP produced a detailed workplan outlining the genotypes to be harvested and the samples to be produced and analyzed. The sampling protocol was discussed at length to ensure enough replications of each genotype were included in the workplans (at planting, harvesting and sample preparation).

The CIP strategy for evaluating potato genotypes based on core traits: firmness, mealiness, and taste (bitterness). Two genotype sets are included. Set 1 comprises 50 genotypes from ten full-sib families, selected for sensory and instrumental texture analysis. Based on glycoalkaloid levels and sensory results, 27 genotypes will be planted in Huancayo and Paucartambo, Peru, in October 2025, with 15 selected for full phenotyping and metabolomics. Set 2 includes five commercial Peruvian varieties with contrasting mealiness, sourced from local markets.

Sampling involves harvesting tubers, slicing them longitudinally, and preparing raw and cooked samples for freeze-drying and metabolomic analysis. Cooked portions are also used for sensory evaluation via Descriptive Sensory Analysis (DSA). Instrumental texture analysis will be performed using penetration testing and, if available, the mini-Kramer Ottawa cell.

Each biological replicate includes 15–18 tubers, with clear labeling and storage protocols. Samples will be shipped to RHUL for metabolomics. Sensory panels will assess flavor, firmness, and mealiness, with Set 2 using an abridged DSA method. A chronogram integrates all activities from planting to sample shipment, ensuring harmonized evaluation across sites.

Key Words: Phenotyping, Descriptive Sensory Analysis (DSA), Instrumental Texture Analysis (TPA), Firmness, Mealiness, Genotype Selection, Metabolomic, Boiled Potato, Traits

1 PHENOTYPING USING HARMONIZED SOPs FOR BOILED POTATO: CORE TRAITS

The core traits for boiled potato are firmness, taste (degree of bitterness after taste) and mealiness. SOPs for sensory evaluation of boiled potato in Uganda <https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00705> and instrumental texture analysis using penetration <https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00783>

2 DEFINITION OF GENOTYPES TO SCREEN.

The potato CIP team has **two sets of genotypes/varieties** available for the RTBfoodomics project.

SET 1: A total of 50 genotypes will be screened for firmness, mealiness, and taste using a rapid sensory method adapted from the Descriptive Sensory Analysis (DSA) method previously published for potatoes. These genotypes belong to ten different full-sib families, each represented by eight genotypes. The progenitors of these families, along with their respective glycoalkaloid levels, are listed in **Table 1**. In addition to sensory evaluation, instrumental texture analysis (penetration testing) will be used to assess firmness. The 50 genotypes are expected to show wide variability in taste quality—ranging from good to intermediate to poor or bitter—based on the glycoalkaloid levels previously measured in the male and female parents of each family (**Table 1**). From this set, 27 genotypes will be selected based on contrasting taste (particularly bitterness) and firmness. Preselection will take place in April/May 2025 at CIP headquarters (**Figure 1**).

The genotypes from SET 1 belong to full-sib families derived from a late blight-resistant potato population (**Table 1**). Genotypes from the families CIP3220106, CIP3220116, CIP3220122, CIP3220126, CIP3220146, CIP3220127, and CIP3220133 are half-siblings, all sharing the same male parent (CIP316344.146). Similarly, genotypes from the families CIP3220114, CIP3220130, and CIP3220137 are half-sibs, with a common male parent (CIP316367.181). Additionally, genotypes from the families CIP3220133 and CIP3220137 share the same female parent (CIP316361.187), while those from families CIP3220127 and CIP3220130 share the same female parent (CIP316361.163).

The 27 selected genotypes will be planted in Huancayo, Peru, in October 2025 and harvested in March 2026. A backup of SET 1 will also be grown in Paucartambo, Peru, during the same period. At each location, a total of 50 plants per genotype will be grown. Although only 35 plants are required (**Figure 1**), additional plants will be included to account for the exclusion of border plants.

Table 1: Description of the ten full-sib families that make up Set 1 of genotypes. Several of these full-sib families share the same male progenitor.

A few also have the same female progenitor. Progenitors offer a wide variation regarding glycoalkaloids concentration.

Family	Female parent Accession #	Glycoalkaloids mg/100, FW	Male parent Accession #	Glycoalkaloids mg/100, FW
CIP3220106	CIP316346.204	5.62	CIP316344.146	5.77
CIP3220116	CIP316356.117	2.17	CIP316344.146	
CIP3220122	CIP316359.134	3.62	CIP316344.146	
CIP3220126	CIP316361.156	2.74	CIP316344.146	
CIP3220146	CIP317008.407	3.36	CIP316344.146	
CIP3220127	CIP316361.163	7.62	CIP316344.146	
CIP3220133	CIP316361.187	10.68	CIP316344.146	
CIP3220114	CIP316355.162	7.61	CIP316367.181	8.61
CIP3220130	CIP316361.163	7.62	CIP316367.181	
CIP3220137	CIP316361.187	10.68	CIP316367.181	

Figure 1: Diagram illustrating the key steps in genotype selection, sample preparation, processing and shipment of potato samples from SET 1.

SET 2: This set includes five Peruvian yellow/cream-fleshed commercial varieties—Peruanita, Amarilla, Canchan, Serranita, and Yungay—with contrasting mealiness levels, as determined using a rapid sensory method adapted from the DSA method mentioned above. Up to 130 medium-sized tubers from these commercial varieties will be purchased from a local market in June 2025. Information about the growing location will be obtained from the vendor (**Figure 2**).

Figure 2: Diagram illustrating the key steps in sample preparation, processing and shipment of potato samples from SET 2.

3 SAMPLING STRATEGY AND EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

3.1 Description of the experimental design

For SET 1:

After the selection made in April/May 2025, SET1 includes only 27 genotypes. A total of 50 plants per genotype will be planted at each of two locations: Huancayo and Paucartambo, with the latter serving as a backup site (**Figure 1**). Five plants from each genotype will be harvested two weeks prior to the planned main harvest date, and 20 tubers will be selected for rapid DSA evaluation. Based on preliminary DSA results, 15 genotypes—five rated as good, five as intermediate, and five as poor for firmness and taste—will be selected for full harvest and phenotyping. For each of these 15 selected genotypes, six biological samples will be prepared for metabolomic analysis at RHUL, as well as for DSA and TPA analyses at CIP-HQ (**Figure 1**). Each biological sample will consist of 15 tubers from five plants: 10 tubers will be used for DSA, and five for TPA.

For SET 2:

One hundred and thirty medium-sized tubers from each of the five Peruvian yellow/cream-fleshed commercial varieties will be purchased from a local market. Although only 108 tubers are required, 130 will be obtained to ensure an adequate sample size. Six biological replicates will be prepared for each variety (**Figure 2**). Each biological sample will consist of 18 tubers: ten tubers will be used to prepare raw and cooked samples for metabolomic analysis and for a rapid DSA evaluation of firmness and mealiness, while the remaining eight tubers will be used for instrumental TPA analysis.

Preparation of samples for metabolomic analysis and DSA/texture phenotyping

Each tuber will be cut longitudinally into two halves. One half will be used to prepare the raw sample for metabolomic analysis, while the other half will be used to prepare the cooked sample for both metabolomic and DSA analyses.

Preparation of raw samples

From the first half of each tuber, a slice (2 mm thick) will be taken from the longitudinal section and immediately placed in a plastic bag. Liquid nitrogen will be added to rapidly freeze the slice. This procedure will be repeated for all ten tubers, resulting in ten individually frozen raw slices. The samples will be stored at -70°C until freeze-drying is performed.

Preparation of cooked samples

The second half of each tuber will be steamed for 20 minutes. After cooking, one slice (as described above) will be taken, placed in a plastic bag, and rapidly frozen using liquid nitrogen. This process will be repeated for all ten tubers, yielding ten individually frozen cooked slices. These samples will also be stored at -70°C until freeze-drying is performed. The remaining portion of each cooked tuber will be reserved for DSA analysis—one portion per participant, for a total of ten participants—for SET 1 samples (**Figure 1**), and for an abridged version of the DSA analysis (focused on mealiness and firmness) for SET 2 samples (**Figure 2**).

Storage and Shipping

Both raw and cooked freeze-dried slices will be stored at -20°C until shipment to RHUL. Each slice will be stored in individual primary packaging to ensure proper homogenization and representative sampling at the laboratory. Packages will be clearly labeled with information including genotype, tuber number, and treatment type (raw or cooked). Samples will be shipped to RHU via a reliable courier service (DHL).

Instrumental texture analysis

From each of the five tubers (for SET 1 genotypes) or each of the eight tubers (for SET 2 varieties), one or two cubes with a diameter of 2.5 cm will be obtained (**Figures 1 and 2**). The instrumental texture of these cubes will be characterized by penetration testing using the P60C conical probe. Additionally, if CIRAD manages to borrow the mini-Kramer Ottawa cell, texture profile analysis (TPA) will also be performed using that device.

3.2 Sensory evaluation of collected samples

For SET 1:

The portion of the cooked tuber remaining after sample collection will be evaluated by a trained panel using the DSA method. This evaluation will focus on attributes related to potato flavor, as well as firmness and mealiness in the mouth.

For SET 2:

The remaining portion of the cooked tuber, after lab sample collection, will be evaluated using an abridged version of the DSA method. This assessment will focus specifically on attributes related to mealiness and firmness in the mouth.

4 CHRONOGRAM OF ACTIVITIES

The information in **Figures 1 and 2** regarding planting, harvesting, processing, and sample shipment dates can be integrated into a chronological timeline of activities leading up to the shipment of samples to the RHUL lab in the UK.

Table 2: Tentative chronogram of activities

SET	Field		Phenotyping (wet lab)		Sensory panel	Sample shipment	
	Planting	Harvest	All clones	Selected clones		Frozen (CIRAD)	Freeze-dried (RHUL)
SET 1	Oct.2025	Mar.2026	April	Apr. – May 2026	Apr. – May 2026		Jun.– Jul.2026
SET 2		Jun.2025		May 2025	Jun.2025		Jul.2025

APPENDICE

Appendix 1. Link to published standard operating procedures.

SOP for sensory evaluation of boiled potato in Uganda	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00705
SOP for sensory characterization of Matooke. Kampala, Uganda	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00593
SOP for sensory characterization of Fufu. Umudike, Nigeria	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00595
SOP for sensory characterization of Eba. Ibadan, Nigeria	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00596
SOP for sensory characterization of pounded yam. Iwo, Nigeria	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00597
SOP for sensory characterization of boiled cassava. Cotonou, Benin	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00598
SOP for sensory characterization of boiled cassava. Kampala, Uganda	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00599
SOP for sensory characterization of boiled yam. Cotonou, Benin	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00600
SOP for sensory evaluation on boiled sweetpotato. Kampala, Uganda	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00601
SOP for sensory characterization of Attiéké. Bingerville, Côte d'Ivoire	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00607
SOP for sensory evaluation of boiled plantain. Abidjan, Côte d'Ivoire	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00606
SOP for sensory evaluation of fried plantain (Aloco). Abidjan, Côte d'Ivoire	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00709
Training a panel in sensory analysis and implementing descriptive tests. How to process data	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00573
Monitoring panel performance and cleaning data from descriptive sensory panels for statistical analysis	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00582
Performances du panel et préparer les données en analyses sensorielles avant les traitements statistiques	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00583
Statistics (PCA and multiple regression) to Visualise Sensory Analysis & Relate it to the Instrumental Data	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00710
Statistiques (ACP et régression multiple) pour Visualiser les Données de l'Analyse Sensorielle et les Relier aux Données Instrumentales	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00738

Standard Operating Protocol for Instrumental Texture Characterization of Boiled Plantain. Njombe, Cameroun	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00685
SOP for characterization of cooking time and texture of boiled cassava: Texture-extrusion. Cali, Colombia	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00594
SOP for sample preparation and texture analysis of Matooke. Kampala, Uganda	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00602
SOP for sample preparation and cooking time for texture analysis of boiled yam. Cotonou, Benin	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00603
SOP for textural characterization of Eba. Ibadan, Nigeria	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00604
SOP for textural characterization of boiled sweetpotato - version A	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00611
SOP for textural characterization of boiled sweetpotato - version B	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00749
SOP for textural characterization of Fufu. Umudike, Nigeria	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00612
SOP for for textural characterization of pounded yam. Iwo, Nigeria	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00613
Standard Operating Protocol for the Instrumental Determination of Extensibility of Pounded yam. Montpellier	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00684

Appendix 1. cont.

SOP for Determination of Bi-extensional viscosity of Pounded yam by Lubricated Squeezing Flow (LSF)	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00686
SOP for sample preparation, determination of instrumental texture of steam-cooked cassava in Benin	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00723
SOP for Firmness of Cassava genotypes during Retting using the hand-held Penetrometer	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00734
SOP for MIRS measurement on cassava cell walls and flours	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00675
Harmonized SOP for NIRS measurement on intact cassava roots and yam tubers using NIRS FOSS	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00665
SOP for NIRS on fresh intact/mashed cassava roots using portable ASD Near Infra-Red Reflectance Spec.	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00678
SOP for NIRS Acquisition on fresh cassava roots using the ASD quality spec (QST) and relating spectra to root dry matter content by oven method	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00668
SOP for NIRS acquisition on fresh cassava roots using the benchtop NIRS FOSS DS2500 and relating spectra to root dry Matter content by oven method	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00669

SOP for Feasibility of Bad-Good Genotypes Screening using NIRS	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00671
SOP for NIRS measurement on milled and un-milled Gari	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00674
SOP for NIRS measurement on fresh ground cassava	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00676
SOP for determination of dry matter content of wet Fufu mash using handheld NIRS	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00677
SOP for NIRS acquisition on fresh Matooke fingers using the benchtop NIRS FOSS DS2500 and relating spectra to finger dry matter content by oven method	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00679
Harmonized SOP for NIRS Measurement on Blended Cassava and Yam using NIRS FOSS	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00706
SOP for near infrared spectroscopy (NIRS) acquisition on sweetpotato roots and potato tubers	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00708
SOP for NIRS Acquisition on fresh cassava roots using FOSS DS2500 & ASD Quality Spec and relating the NIRS spectra to fresh HCN content by picrate method	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00747
Operating mode and parameters configuration of hyperspectral camera Specim FX17	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00667
SOP for hyperspectral imaging analysis of fresh RTB crops	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00666
SOP for calibrated color measurements of RTB foods using image analysis	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00663
SOP for characterization of RTB starch grain size and shape through Imaging	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00670
SOP for characterization of RTB product colour change during time	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00672
Creation of a color reference chart for RTB foods colour characterization	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00673
SOP for image capture in sweetpotato and potato, and sensory attribute prediction	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00721
SOP for DigiEye Calibration	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00722
SOP for colour measurement in fresh yam (<i>Dioscorea Sp.</i>) and fresh cassava using chromameter	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00664
State of Knowledge on breeding for quality Roots, Tubers and Cooking Bananas	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00741
Appendix 1. cont.	
SOP for Instrumental Textural Characterization of Fried Plantain (Aloco)	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00781

SOP for Characterization of Instrumental Texture of Steamed Potato by Penetration, TPA and Extrusion	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00783
SOP for Sample Preparation and the Measurement of Texture of Boiled Yam	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00786
SOP for Determination of Extensibility of Pounded Yam using Kieffer Dough Extensibility Method	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00787
SOP for Textural Characterization of Boiled Yam by Ottawa Extrusion	N/A
SOP for Characterization of Instrumental Color of Raw Matooke	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00782
Training & Support Mission on Instrumental Textural Characterization of Extensibility of Pounded Yam by Uniaxial Extension and Bi-extensional Viscosity at CNRA & UNA, Côte d'Ivoire	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00780
Training & Support Mission on Hyperspectral Imaging (HSI) at CIAT, Colombia	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00784
Relationship between Sensory and Instrumental Stretchability of Pounded Yam	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00785

